

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

WP8 – Communication, dissemination and exploitation

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	688363	Acronym	hackAIR	
Full Title	Collective awareness platform for outdoor air pollution			
Start Date	1 st January 2016	Duration	36 months	
Project URL	www.hackAIR.eu			
Deliverable	D 8.1 – Communication and Dissemination Strategy			
Work Package	WP 8 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	1 st April 2016	Actual	31 st March 2016
Nature	Report	Dissemination Level	Public	
Lead Beneficiary	ONSUB			
Responsible Author	Wiebke Herding			
Contributions from	Christodoulos Keratidis (DRAXIS), Panagiota Syropoulou (DRAXIS), Hai-Ying-Liu (NILU), Symeon Papadopoulos (CERTH), Anastasia Moumtzidou (CERTH), Arne Fellerman (BUND), Paulien Coppens (VUB), Inge Jansen (ONSUB), Fabiola Benavente (ONSUB).			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
1.0	01/03/2016	Draft	First draft	ONSUB
1.1	23/03/2016	Draft	Draft for review	All partners
1.3	24/03/2016	Final	Final version	Review by DRAXIS

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© hackAIR Consortium, 2016

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

1	Executive summary.....	6
2	About hackAIR	6
2.1	The hackAIR project.....	6
2.2	The hackAIR platform	6
3	Situation analysis and context	7
3.1	Political and legislative context.....	9
3.2	Economic context	9
3.3	Social context.....	10
3.4	Technological context.....	10
4	Target audiences and messaging.....	10
4.1	hackAIR network of interest	12
4.1.1	Important subgroups	12
4.1.2	Current assumptions	12
4.1.3	Desired outcomes.....	12
4.1.4	Main engagement channels	13
4.2	hackAIR network of interest: core group.....	13
4.2.1	Current assumptions	13
4.2.2	Desired outcomes.....	13
4.2.3	Main channels of engagement	14
4.2.4	Important subgroups	14
4.2.5	Current assumptions	14
4.2.6	Desired outcomes.....	15
4.2.7	Main engagement channels	15
5	Communication objectives	15
6	Activities and expected results	15
6.1	Start – up phase.....	16
6.1.1	Output 1.1: hackAIR communication toolkit.....	16
6.1.2	Activity 1.1.1: Project website	16
6.1.2.1	Goals and audiences	17
6.1.2.2	Activities	17
6.1.2.3	Indicative timeline	18
6.1.2.4	Expected result	18
6.1.3	Activity 1.1.2: Communication material	18
6.1.3.1	Goals and audience	19
6.1.3.2	Activities	19

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

6.1.3.3	Indicative timeline	19
6.1.3.4	Expected result	20
6.1.4	Output 1.2: Audience engagement	20
6.1.5	Activity 1.2.1: Newsletter	20
6.1.5.1	Goals and audiences	20
6.1.5.2	Activities	20
6.1.5.3	Indicative timeline	21
6.1.5.4	Expected result	21
6.1.6	Activity 1.2.2: Network of interest	21
6.1.6.1	Goals and audiences	21
6.1.6.2	Activities	22
6.1.6.3	Indicative timeline	22
6.1.6.4	Expected result	22
6.2	Pilot phase	22
6.2.1	Output 2.1: Buzz and engagement	23
6.2.2	Activity 2.1.1: Social media	23
6.2.2.1	Goals and audience	23
6.2.2.2	Activities	23
6.2.2.3	Indicative timeline	25
6.2.2.4	Expected result	25
6.2.3	Activity 2.1.2: Direct communication support for the pilot	25
6.2.3.1	Goals and audience	25
6.2.3.2	Activities	25
6.2.3.3	Indicative timeline	26
6.2.3.4	Expected result	26
6.2.4	Output 2.2: Hands-on opportunities to experience the platform	26
6.2.5	Activity 2.2.1: hackAIR workshop tour	26
6.2.5.1	Goals and audience	26
6.2.5.2	Indicative timeline	27
6.2.5.3	Expected result	27
6.3	Sustainability phase	27
6.3.1	Output 3.1: Expand the network	27
6.3.2	Activity 3.1.1: External meetings	27
6.3.2.1	Goals and audience	27
6.3.2.2	Activities	27
6.3.2.3	Initial list of events	28
6.3.2.4	Expected result	28

Table of Figures

Table 1 - Characteristics of the hackAIR platform.....	7
Figure 1 - Annual mean PM10 concentrations in 2013 in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. EU target value = 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, WHO air quality guideline = 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	8
Figure 2 - Annual mean PM2.5 concentrations in 2013 in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. EU target value = 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, WHO air quality guideline = 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	8
Table 2 – Prioritised overview of target audiences.....	11
Figure 3 - Indicative implementation timeline.....	16
Figure 4 - Website homepage.....	18
Figure 5. Recommended safe space around the logo.....	36

1 Executive summary

This document contains Deliverable 8.1 (Communication and dissemination strategy) for the project hackAIR. It is also referred to as “Communication Strategy”. It contains:

- a description of the context in which hackAIR’s communication takes place;
- a discussion of hackAIR’s target audience groups and appropriate messaging and framing;
- the organisation and implementation of the project’s dissemination activities and events; and
- monitoring and reporting provisions.

The strategy will be implemented through the following tasks:

- Task 8.2: Dissemination content & activities;
- Task 8.3: hackAIR workshop tour; and
- Task 8.4: Establishment and management of network of interest.

The detailed implementation of hackAIR’s communication and dissemination activities will build on synergies with the following project deliverables:

- D2.4 Report on co-creation of services;
- D6.1 Engagement strategy for hackAIR community involvement;
- D6.2 Behavioural change techniques for hackAIR community; and
- D7.1 Pilot plan.

Based on these documents, hackAIR will produce an update to the present document in M21.

2 About hackAIR

2.1 The hackAIR project

hackAIR is an EU-funded project aiming to develop an open technology platform for citizen observatories on air quality. It is supported through the EU programme on “Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation” until December 2018.

Following a co-creation process with users (WP2) and the development of the hackAIR platform and its components (WP3-5), the hackAIR platform will be pilot tested in Norway and Germany starting in September 2017 (WP7). In order to inform about the pilot and to provide their communication, WP6 explores engagement strategies for user participation.

2.2 The hackAIR platform

The hackAIR platform will be composed of a website and a complementary mobile application that provides citizens with improved information about air pollution levels where they live. It complements official data with a number of community-driven data sources, including:

- an easy-to-build open hardware sensor module that transmits regular air quality measurements via Bluetooth;
- air quality information derived from mobile phone pictures of the sky; and
- a low-tech measurement setup involving paper filters and aquarium air pumps.

Based on the hackAIR web platform, organisations and communities of citizens can create a community portal to freely publish and access air quality data under their own brand (‘powered by hackAIR’).

Table 1 summarises the characteristics of the hackAIR platform.

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Table 1 - Characteristics of the hackAIR platform

What hackAIR is	What hackAIR is not
Open	A provider of scientifically precise data
Distributed	Available everywhere
Participatory	Low effort (with regards to the hardware sensors)
Low-cost	Covering all aspects of air quality
Locally relevant	A provider of scientifically precise data
User-friendly	

3 Situation analysis and context

To better understand the context in which hackAIR's communication activities would need to be successful, this chapter presents a brief political, economic, social, environmental, legal and technological analysis of issues and trends concerning citizen engagement on air quality monitoring in Europe.

Air pollution is an important environmental and social problem, as it leads to a multitude of adverse effects on human health, ecosystems, the built environment, and our climate. At the same time it is a highly complex problem. Effective action to reduce the impacts of air pollution requires holistic solutions, involving among others technological development and up-to-date knowledge of the status of air quality¹.

Air quality in Europe is slowly improving. However, between 2000 and 2013 a significant proportion of the urban population in the EU28 was exposed to concentrations of certain air pollutants above EU limit or target values. The number of people exposed was even higher in relation to the more stringent World Health Organisation (WHO) air quality guideline value set for the protection of human health.

Particulate matter (PM), one of the most important pollutants in the field next to the other pollutants, is the focus of the hackAIR project.

For fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), 4-14% of the urban population was exposed to concentrations in excess of the EU target value, while 87-98% was exposed to concentrations above the WHO guideline value (for 2006-2013 only). For coarse particulate matter (PM₁₀), the respective exposure estimates were 17-41% for the EU limit value and 61-92% for the WHO guideline value².

¹ European Environment Agency (2015). Air quality in Europe – 2015 report. Available at <http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/air-quality-in-europe-2015>

² European Environment Agency (2015). Exceedance of air quality limit values in urban areas. Available at <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/exceedance-of-air-quality-limit-3/assessment-1>

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Figure 1 - Annual mean PM10 concentrations in 2013 in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. EU target value = $40 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, WHO air quality guideline = $20 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$

Figure 2 - Annual mean PM2.5 concentrations in 2013 in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. EU target value = $25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, WHO air quality guideline = $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Every year over 400,000 people in the EU die prematurely due to the consequences of air pollution and another 6.5 million people fall sick due to diseases caused by air pollution. Air pollution also harms the natural environment: almost two thirds of Europe's ecosystems are endangered due to the effects of air pollution³.

3.1 Political and legislative context

On a global level, the World Health Organisation establishes the main air quality guidelines for particulate matter, ozone, nitrogen dioxide, and sulphur dioxide⁴. These guideline values are more stringent than the target values set by the EU Air Quality Directive. Directive 2008/50/EC came into force in 2008 and establishes air quality objectives and corrective actions until 2020. It requires member states to monitor and assess air quality, to report monitoring and assessment results to the European Commission and the public (including environmental, consumer and other relevant organisations) and to implement air quality plans^{5 6}.

In December 2013 the European Commission published a new EU clean air policy package demanding for extra effort on European level. Between 2011 and 2013 a stakeholder expert group consisting of member states, industry, NGOs and international stakeholders was consulted for the review of the air pollution policy. Directive 2008/50/EC will probably be revised starting in 2021.

At local level, several municipalities throughout Europe have implemented measures to reduce the burden of harmful substances in the air to a level that is insignificant for humans and the environment, e.g. through Low Emission Zones⁷. Many cities have taken an active role in air quality monitoring, often also required by law to do so. Examples of intentionally moving monitoring equipment away from busy roads are also reported⁸. EURO CITIES, the network of major European cities, has a working group on air quality, climate change & energy efficiency that works on providing EU institutions with a city perspective on the EU air quality policy and collects best practice examples of improving air quality and implementing EU legislation in cities⁹.

3.2 Economic context

The main sources for air pollution are industry, transport, energy production and distribution, and agricultural activities, as well as some domestic household activities like heating. The cost of air pollution¹⁰ is estimated to be €15bn from lost workdays, €4bn for healthcare costs, €3bn from crop yield loss and €1bn from damages on buildings. Health-related external costs range between €330 billion and €940 billion per year depending on the valuation methodology.

Road transport is an important source of air pollutants. Emissions from vehicles lead to concentrations of air pollutants above EU standards in many European cities. Around 12% of primary EU PM_{2.5} emissions come from road transport¹¹. Since vehicle pollution generally occurs in populated areas, pollutants released by road transport cause a high population exposure. Industrial facilities are another important source of emissions of air pollutants. 1% of

³ European Commission (2013). Cleaner air for all. Available at http://ec.europa.eu/environment/air/cleaner_air/index.html

⁴ World Health Organisation. Air quality guidelines. Available at http://www.who.int/phe/health_topics/outdoorair/outdoorair_agg/en/

⁵ EUR-Lex. Summary Directive 2008/50/EC. Available at <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/LSU/?uri=CELEX:32008L0050>

⁶ Andrews, A. (2015). Clean Air Handbook version 2. Available at <http://www.clientearth.org/health-environment/health-environment-publications/clean-air-handbook-updated-for-2015-3091>

⁷ Clean Air (2015). Downloads. <http://www.cleanair-europe.org/en/downloads/>

⁸ Clean Air Handbook, see above.

⁹ EURO CITIES. Working group air quality, climate change & energy efficiency. Available at http://www.eurocities.eu/eurocities/working_groups/Air-quality-climate-change-energy-efficiency&tpl=home

¹⁰ European Commission (2013). The Clean Air Policy Package. Commission Staff Working Document. Available at http://ec.europa.eu/environment/archives/air/pdf/Impact_assessment_en.pdf

¹¹ European Environment Agency (2016). Explaining road transport emissions. A non-technical guide. Available at <http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/explaining-road-transport-emissions>

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

plants are responsible for 50% of the damage of which the top 30 are mainly coal/lignite fuelled power-generating facilities, located predominantly in Germany and Eastern Europe¹².

3.3 Social context

On a social level, many organisations across Europe have been active in raising awareness on air pollution. Increasing attention is given to public participation in data collection, allowing members of the public to play an active part in monitoring and recording the state of their environment. Important approaches are citizen science (commonly defined as “scientific work undertaken by members of the general public, often in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists and scientific institutions”) and citizen observatories, assisting citizens in observing and understanding environmental issues, as well as reporting and commenting on them with the help of advanced information technology¹³. A recent survey carried out in Sweden shows that nine out of ten people believe it is important for the public to be involved in research and nearly six out of ten would like to get personally involved. Health came out as the main research area of involvement, followed by energy and climate¹⁴. Recent examples include [senseBox](#) (do-it-yourself-toolkit for stationary and mobile sensor stations - a citizen science toolkit for everybody) and [CITI-SENSE](#) (with eight citizen observatories for outdoor air quality).

3.4 Technological context

AirBase is the European air quality database maintained by the European Environmental Agency (EEA), containing air quality monitoring data and information submitted by participating countries throughout Europe. All member states have an air quality monitoring network in place, although the minimum requirements allow for variations between states. There is a lack of up-to-date information on air quality levels, with data published a long time after breaches of limit values have occurred and in highly technical formats, which are often difficult to be interpreted¹⁵.

There are several projects to improve air quality data and to make it easily accessible. Areas include the supplementation official data with other air quality data (e.g. through biomonitoring in Antwerp - [AIRbezen](#)), delivering personalised environmental information from multiple sources to users (e.g. [PESCaDO](#) or [ENVI4ALL](#) app for targeted, localised, and easy-to-understand information on air quality information), making open source technology available to citizens (e.g. [Smart Citizen](#)), or creating measurement tools ([iSPEX](#), an optical sensor for smartphones that measures aerosol properties). The scale and time slot of the information made available to citizens varies and the accuracy of the data is often unknown. [AirBase](#) publishes data with a delay of 1.5 years, with annual and daily mean concentration from almost 1,000 stations. An app like [Plume Labs](#) provides information on air pollution for most cities with a delay of 2-3 hours, but manages to display real-time information and a forecast of the pollution in Paris.

4 Target audiences and messaging

In order to achieve these objectives hackAIR needs to effectively communicate with two different target audience groups. This chapter describes who they are, what sub-groups they are composed of, their motivations and possible influencing approaches. A complete list of audiences by category is included in the annex.

hackAIR’s main target audiences have been identified as follows:

¹² European Environment Agency (2014). Costs of air pollution from European industrial facilities 2008–2012 — an updated assessment. Available at <http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/costs-of-air-pollution-2008-2012>

¹³ Grossberndt, S. & Liu, H-Y. (2016). Citizen participation approaches in environmental health.

¹⁴ VA (2016). VA Barometer 2015/2016. Available at <http://v-a.se/2016/02/va-barometer-20152016-english/>

¹⁵ Clean Air Handbook, see above.

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

1. **hackAIR network of interest.** This group is composed of organisations and institutions with a general interest in the field of participatory sensing and/or air quality. These networks have an interest in engaging with the hackAIR project by
 - Using hackAIR’s data to gain insights into air quality patterns;
 - Providing input regarding the platform design; or
 - Using open source software / hardware in their own applications.
2. **hackAIR community.** This group is composed of the primary users of the hackAIR platform, who are motivated by environmental or health concerns. They have an interest in engaging with the hackAIR platform by
 - Submitting data through the hackAIR interface;
 - Building a dedicated air quality monitoring station; and
 - Organising local hackAIR workshops and using the project to raise awareness.

The next sections provide more detailed information about each of the target audiences; specific communication activities and tactics are discussed further below.

As part of Work Package 2, hackAIR partner organisations rated the target end users of the project as follows¹⁶:

Table 2 – Prioritised overview of target audiences

Audience	Type of user	Examples	Priority
Network of Interest	Environmental organisations	NGOs (e.g., Bund, Greenpeace)	High
	Policy makers/decision makers	Municipalities	High
	Researchers/scientists		Medium
	App developers	Researchers of commercial and non-commercial research institutes	Low
	Environmental organisations	Individual app developers, SMEs	High
Community	People with a higher health risk related to air pollution	People with respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, allergies (e.g., pollen))	High
		Elderly people	Medium
	People with concerns for future generations	Parents of young children	High
		Pregnant women	Medium
	People with higher exposure to air pollution	Athletes or other people exercising outdoors (e.g., cyclists, joggers, hikers)	High
		Place of residence: people who live in (highly) polluted areas (e.g., in a busy street, near airports, large animal stables, canals/rivers with a lot of ship traffic...)	Medium
	Multipliers	Persons with an environmental interest	High
		Environmental activists	High
		Members of environmental organization	High
		Persons with a health interest	Medium
		Makerspaces	Medium
		(Daily) news media	Medium

¹⁶ Adapted version from T2.1: Delineation of key concepts and key components of the hackAIR platform (Draft, March 2016)

4.1 hackAIR network of interest

These are organisations, researchers, institutions, and technology developers interested in using technology and/or citizen science to improve air quality. They all share a key concern for better monitoring and data and/or for increasing citizen engagement. In the first 18 months of the project, the networks of interest are the **only** target audience of the hackAIR project since the hackAIR platform will not yet be sufficiently developed for communication to users.

4.1.1 Important subgroups

1. Organisations working on public health and/or environmental issues. Examples include: European Environmental Bureau, the Norwegian Asthma and Allergy Association and Model City Copenhagen.
2. Institutions conducting research and monitoring on air quality and pollution. Examples include: public authorities all over Europe (especially municipalities), national research institutes, and local citizen science projects like Curieuzeneuzen in Antwerp or the Amsterdam Smart Citizens Labs.
3. Businesses and projects collecting, managing, and displaying air quality data. Examples include: AirBase, the public air quality database system of the EEA, projects like CAPTOR providing better availability of information on national level and app developers working on local air quality information like Plume Labs.

The structure for the hackAIR stakeholder database can be found in Annex 6.

4.1.2 Current assumptions

The identified stakeholders are looking for data on air quality patterns, are interested in examples and lessons learned of citizen science and observatories or looking for new initiatives in the areas of open source software/hardware or open data to use for dedicated applications.

What they might think	What they might feel	What they might do
<p>“Air quality is really important. Providing more data to citizens will help them change their behaviour.”</p> <p>“This is a complex issue, and we need to know more.”</p> <p>“Nobody understands air quality; we’re struggling to raise awareness.”</p> <p>“Air quality measurements should be done scientifically, not by newbies.”</p> <p>“Why would air pollution be important? Why should I care?”</p>	<p>Overwhelmed</p> <p>Disconnected</p> <p>Cynical</p>	<p>Build their own data portal or information platform</p> <p>Involve citizens on local level</p>

4.1.3 Desired outcomes

Given the large geographic range of the hackAIR project and its large potential user base, the project will employ a networked approach to communication and focus on identifying strategically located and connected partner organisations that can serve as multipliers and disseminate communication about the project to citizens and potential users.

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

In an ecosystem full of emerging initiatives on air quality information and community monitoring, hackAIR will approach existing stakeholders, networks and initiatives in a collaborative manner: Citizens have a right to access better air quality data, and they can benefit from better integration and coordination of data sources and existing initiatives. In doing so, hackAIR can benefit from other organisations' lessons learned, feedback and ideas by building a better product and increasing its viability over time.

What we want them to think	What we want them to feel	What we want them to do
<p>"We are part of a growing movement working with citizens to improve air quality data"</p> <p>"We see our work having an impact"</p> <p>"More and more people are getting involved"</p> <p>"Now I understand air pollution better, it actually is a big problem and I should care more."</p>	<p>Engaged</p> <p>Empowered</p> <p>Informed</p>	<p>Use data generated by hackAIR and other sources to gain insights on air quality patterns</p> <p>Use the open hardware and software behind the hackAIR platform in dedicated air quality applications</p> <p>Give input on platform development and promote the use of the platform to dedicated networks</p>

4.1.4 Main engagement channels

The network of interest will receive our newsletter every six months in which we inform about the project, share new project developments, give first updates from the technology team, and share interesting articles. In addition, we will reach out to relevant communities through presentations at conferences and meetings and keep people informed regularly with updates on social media and on the website.

4.2 hackAIR network of interest: core group

In addition to a wider network of interest, we will build a deeper relationship with a smaller core group of stakeholders. The core group will consist of 15-20 people (composed of the same subgroups as above) who will be actively involved in the project development, this group will be in regular contact with exchange via an email group and webinars, and members will be invited to one or two stakeholder workshops.

4.2.1 Current assumptions

People involved in similar projects or research areas have a genuine interest in sharing their own experience and data, expand or merge databases, develop a common narrative and exchange lessons learned. They want to participate in regular mail exchange to discuss the link between air quality and citizen science, hot topics, other relevant initiatives and reality checks. They are willing to participate in stakeholder workshops and to add data, new insights, and critical remarks to the platform.

4.2.2 Desired outcomes

The purpose of the core group is to embed hackAIR within a broader network of projects so that parties can use lessons learned from past projects and have an overview of where related projects overlap and can work together. The resulting insights will inform the design of the hackAIR platform. In addition, the group will be invited to collaborate on joint statements or guiding principles to reach beyond the dedicated network in order to influence policies and the public.

4.2.3 Main channels of engagement

In addition to the channels identified above for the wider network of interest, we will use the following approaches:

- ♥ Personal invitations (by email, phone, face-to-face)
- ♥ Regular contact and exchange through an email group
- ♥ 1 -2 stakeholder meetings

4.2.4 Important subgroups

1. Patients with respiratory diseases (such as asthma or allergies) and/or cardiovascular impairments, including the elderly
2. Parents, teachers and other individuals taking care of small children¹⁷
3. People who exercise outdoors, e.g. joggers, cyclists, hikers

hackAIR will mostly rely on intermediaries to communicate with these groups, including:

- ♥ Local media (including newspapers, blogs and social media)
- ♥ Direct targeting through social media (including advertising)
- ♥ Members and supporters of local air quality groups (e.g. Friends of the Earth Germany/BUND)

To build the movement, we will start by focusing on pilot activities in Norway and Germany. In a second step, we will offer the hackAIR platform to other places with existing air quality initiatives that are willing to host a local workshop. Finally, we will open up our communication to reach individuals across Europe.

4.2.5 Current assumptions

Air pollution is the single environmental issue Europeans worry about most, and many do not feel sufficiently informed about air quality issues in their country. Air pollution is mostly perceived as a local issue, with strong variations depending on the location, time of day and weather. Citizens have many reasons to be concerned about air quality: the most pressing concerns are related to respiratory health. This is of particular interest to people who exercise outdoors, who look after children or the elderly, or who suffer from respiratory problems themselves.

What they might think	What they might feel	What they might do
"I am concerned about the quality of the air my children breathe." "I sometimes have difficulty breathing." "I don't think the national government, the city, the factory, etc. is doing enough to clean up the air where I live."	Uninformed Concerned Helpless	Check official air quality data or use an app Write to public officials Choose to wear a face mask or to not go out at certain times of the day

¹⁷ This includes pregnant women.

4.2.6 Desired outcomes

What we want them to think	What we want them to feel	What we want them to do
“It was fun to build my own air quality sensor together with others.”	Connected	Use the hackAIR platform to submit and review air quality data
“I now know so much more about the air I breathe.”	In charge	Build and maintain an air quality monitoring station
“I know what to do to improve air quality – and I’m inviting others to join me.”	Informed	Link up with others locally and build awareness of air quality issues
	Part of community	
	Leaders	

4.2.7 Main engagement channels

The detailed communication plan to engage the hackAIR community will be in line with the following deliverables:

- D6.1 Engagement strategy for hackAIR community involvement
- D6.2 Behavioural change techniques for hackAIR community
- D7.1 Pilot plan

Channels will include the hackAIR website, social media engagement and media outreach. A series of workshops will help to build the hackAIR community in selected locations. In addition, communication efforts will also be put towards supporting partners in their communication work, e.g. by summarising and rewriting publications and invitations in clear language to reach out to the local municipality and citizens’ organisations and supplying promotional products for presentations of partners at conferences and events.

5 Communication objectives

The overall objective of the hackAIR communication strategy is:

To encourage communities of citizens to easily set up air quality monitoring networks and engage their members in measuring and publishing outdoor air pollution levels.

This objective is supported by the following specific objectives:

1. Encourage stakeholder activities around air quality monitoring and encourage citizen participation in the hackAIR platform;
2. Build awareness and foster citizen engagement on air quality issues through the hackAIR platform; and
3. Build interest in the use of the hackAIR platform and in monitoring data beyond the lifetime of the hackAIR project.

6 Activities and expected results

The activities required to achieve the objectives above will be implemented across three distinct phases (after the initial setup and planning stage):

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

1. **Start-up phase:** Building awareness and interest in the wider air quality community (ca. months 3-18 and onwards)
2. **Pilot phase:** User engagement and pilot operation (ca. months 19-30; preparation starts earlier)
3. **Sustainability phase:** Exploitation, evaluation and dissemination of results (ca. months 31-36; preparation starts earlier)

Individual target audiences and activities can therefore support and sustain each other: Organisations in the network of interest will be invited to support the participation of citizens during the pilot and at other locations. The growing momentum of the hackAIR platform and its use will ensure the sustainability and exploitation of the project.

Figure 3 - Indicative implementation timeline

6.1 Start – up phase

Activities during the start-up phase aim to encourage stakeholder's active engagement and leadership on air quality monitoring and citizen participation and to invite participation in the hackAIR open platform (Objective 1). Activities include:

- 1.1 Providing information about the project through hackAIR's communication toolkit:
 - 1.1.1 Project website; and
 - 1.1.2 Communication material.
- 1.2 Regularly engaging target audiences through:
 - 1.2.1 Newsletters; and
 - 1.2.2 Network of interest.

6.1.1 Output 1.1: hackAIR communication toolkit

hackAIR's communication toolkit aims to provide information about the project in a consistent, easy to understand and professional manner, both at local level for the pilot and at European level.

The information about the project, activities and progress will be circulated through:

- 1.1.1 Project website; and
- 1.1.2 Communication material.

6.1.2 Activity 1.1.1: Project website

The project website (www.hackair.eu) builds the core of hackAIR's communication infrastructure. It will build the hub to all communications. All project information will be publicly available on this site, including static project information, dynamic project updates, the architecture, resources such as training material and presentations, information about air quality and other communication material.

6.1.2.1 Goals and audiences

- 📍 Inform interested parties about the project, activities, air quality, and resources.
- 📍 Inform partners, stakeholders and networks of interest on the progress made and showcase results and achievements.
- 📍 Engage participants in the network of interest in the project co-creation and implementation, inviting them to receive news and updates (through hackAIR's newsletter), register their interest and share their data sources and needs (through a questionnaire).
- 📍 Serve as an information hub for the air quality community, with related initiatives and tools on air quality, contributing to coherence.

Project partners will visit the project website, as well as organisations working on air quality, application developers, media, networks of interest, the general public and (later) to users of the hackAIR platform.

6.1.2.2 Activities

The website aims to present information about the project while providing a simple navigation through different components. Main components are:

- 📍 Home: a brief description of the project, call-to-action and list of project partners;
- 📍 About: a more detailed description of the project, the problem, the project's approach, partners and a timeline;
- 📍 How it works: a description of hackAIR's platform, the technology approach and data sources;
- 📍 Get involved: ways to participate, including signing up to receive the project newsletter, participation in the co-creation process, attendance of hackAIR workshops/events, participation via social media and discovery of related projects and tools;
- 📍 News and events: an information hub with news, updates, and results from hackAIR, workshops, resources and communication material, as well as related initiatives and air quality tools.
- 📍 Contact: contact details and a contact form to get in touch with hackAIR.

During the pilot phase the purpose of the website will expand to:

- 📍 The new project branding;
- 📍 Engagement of hackAIR platform users through videos and online tutorials on the platform use;
- 📍 Stories and use cases for event organisers and hackAIR platform users.

In order to drive traffic to the website all other communication channels and outreach activities (social media, newsletters, workshops, etc.) will link to it. In addition, search engine optimisation and social media paid advertisements will be set up to drive traffic to the site.

The website will be created and managed using a Wordpress content management platform using the Joyn theme as layout. The website's traffic will be tracked using Piwik, an open-source web analytics platform. The setup process of the website will involve project partners to define the content, to actively make it visible and to drive traffic.

Figure 4 - Website homepage

6.1.2.3 Indicative timeline

Month	Date	Description
M1	Jan 2016	Placeholder website online
M3	Mar 2016	Website hackair.eu launches
M20	Aug 2017	Additional website for the hackAIR platform

6.1.2.4 Expected result

Indicator	Means of verification	Target
Total visits (including returning visitors) to the project website	Piwik Analytics	Total: 36,000

The biannual reports will also include an overview of time spent per page and number of pages visited.

6.1.3 Activity 1.1.2: Communication material

In order to build a consistent brand around hackAIR, a set of guidelines is available as part of the project’s visual identity (see annex 4: [Visual identity guidelines](#)).

The project’s printed and digital material will be aligned with these guidelines, allowing partners to distribute project information at events, conferences, and meetings related to hackAIR. A second set of visual identity guidelines will be prepared for the hackAIR platform in the second year of the project.

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

6.1.3.1 Goals and audience

Provide information about the project and results, distributed by project partners at events, conferences, and meetings;

Encourage engagement of stakeholders at various occasions; and

Create interest in citizen science on air quality.

The main users of the hackAIR communication material are project partners, event organisers and users of the hackAIR platform.

6.1.3.2 Activities

The production of communication material includes:

- ♥ **Visual identity and branding**, a set of guidelines to communicate consistently.
- ♥ **Presentation**, for use by project partners in events and meetings, with information about hackAIR, project outcomes, the platform architecture and use, as well as air quality. It will be in PowerPoint format.
- ♥ **Brochure**, 2-page leaflet for use by project partners at events and meetings containing information about the project and platform architecture as well as air quality; the leaflet will be circulated in printed and digital (PDF) format.
- ♥ **Postcards and posters**, for event organisers and project partners to create interest in citizen science on air quality and foster engagement. These will contain brief information about hackAIR, citizen science on air quality, and will invite to visit hackAIR's website.
- ♥ **An online tutorial (M27)**, for event organisers and users of the hackAIR platform showing how the hackAIR platform works will be available on the website. It will be uploaded to social media for additional exposure.
- ♥ **A video**, for event organisers and project partners to inform and engage the wider community by showing results of the project. The video will include background information, interactive stories and will be available on the website and uploaded to social media (Youtube) for additional exposure.

6.1.3.3 Indicative timeline

Month	Date	Description	Deliverable
M3	Mar 2016	Visual identity and branding	
M4	Apr 2016	hackAIR presentation	
M6	Jun 2016	Brochure + postcards; Information package	
M10	Oct 2016	Dissemination pack	D8.3
M18	Jun 2017	Provide "summary for publication"	
M20	Aug 2017	Project rebranding; Posters	
M21	Sep 2017	Online tutorial	
M27	Mar 2018	Video showing initial project results	
M36	Dec 2018	Provide "summary for publication" including final results	

6.1.3.4 Expected result

hackAIR's communication material provides comprehensive, high-quality information on the project, making it easy to distribute it at events, conferences, and meetings that are related to hackAIR.

Indicator	Means of verification	Target
Quality and comprehensiveness	Biannual survey among project partners	Average ratings of 4 or above on Likert scale

6.1.4 Output 1.2: Audience engagement

hackAIR's communication aims to regularly engage target audiences through:

1.2.1 Newsletters; and

1.2.2 Networks of Interest.

6.1.5 Activity 1.2.1: Newsletter

hackAIR will produce a newsletter informing stakeholders and interested parties about the project's progress with information about new resources regarding air quality and about recent developments.

6.1.5.1 Goals and audiences

- Disseminate information to organisations working on air quality and to parties interested in the project activities and progress made.
- Engage members of the network of interest in activities and collaborations.
- Inform about related resources (initiatives, tools, events) and developments in air quality, citizen science and behaviour change.

6.1.5.2 Activities

At least six newsletters will be produced during the project. Each edition will mainly be disseminated to the hackAIR email list, published on the website and announced through social media channels for further dissemination. In addition, partners will be invited to circulate the newsletter through their communication channels and networks.

hackAIR's newsletter email list will be sourced through:

- The website, with calls-to-action inviting visitors to sign up for news and updates; and
- Via the network of interest, sourced from project partners by target audiences.

The newsletter will be setup, delivered and monitored through Mailchimp. Where possible, it will contain links to articles on the website.

6.1.5.3 Indicative timeline

Month	Date	Description
M4	Apr 2016	Newsletter issue #1: The case for participatory sensing on air quality: introducing hackAIR
M9	Sep 2016	Newsletter issue #2: Using technology to improve air quality: hackAIR technology foundations and related initiatives
M15	Mar 2017	Newsletter issue #3: Sneak preview: The hackAIR architecture – and insights into user needs
M21	Sep 2017	Newsletter issue #4: Pilot and insights into behaviour change
M27	Mar 2018	Newsletter issue #5: Collaboration with other initiatives – outlook into sustainability and exploitation
M33	Sep 2018	Newsletter issue #6: Review of the hackAIR project
M4	Apr 2016	Newsletter issue #1: The case for participatory sensing on air quality: introducing hackAIR
M9	Sep 2016	Newsletter issue #2: Using technology to improve air quality: hackAIR technology foundations and related initiatives
M15	Mar 2017	Newsletter issue #3: Sneak preview: The hackAIR architecture – and insights into user needs

6.1.5.4 Expected result

NGOs and other civil society organisations are regularly engaged through hackAIR newsletters with a growing number of subscribers.

Indicator	Means of verification	Target
Newsletter impressions	Number of subscribers by issue	Total: 3,000

The biannual reports will also report on delivery rates and opening rates.

6.1.6 Activity 1.2.2: Network of interest

hackAIR's network of interest will facilitate communication and engagement with stakeholder organisations.

6.1.6.1 Goals and audiences

- 📌 Collaborate with umbrella organisations and multipliers to build on existing awareness levels;
- 📌 Amplify hackAIR's credibility, through endorsements by credible institutions and by making it easy for interested parties to get information on the approach and latest developments;
- 📌 Build on the growing momentum of the hackAIR platform and its use;
- 📌 Invite support and participation of citizens in the pilot and in the implementation in other locations;
- 📌 Ensure the continuation of relationships between partners, target audiences, and stakeholders, through a series of communication activities with selected stakeholder organisations; and
- 📌 Support the sustainability and exploitation of the project.

The network of interest includes organisations, researchers, institutions, and developers.

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

6.1.6.2 Activities

- 📍 Intake interviews with hackAIR partners and selected stakeholders
- 📍 Stakeholder database following the target audiences
- 📍 Mapping and priority selection in collaboration with partner BUND
- 📍 Invitations informing about hackAIR, inviting to an information call or a webinar
- 📍 Email group led by BUND to sustain engagement and information exchange
- 📍 Stakeholder meetings, report and press release about main results
- 📍 Network of interest workshop report.

The network of interest and its mailing list will be led and facilitated by BUND. BUND will organise external meetings with the network of interest and hackAIR's representation.

Partners of hackAIR are invited to engage with key people and organisations of the network of interest to develop relationships and encourage participation in project activities.

6.1.6.3 Indicative timeline

Month	Date	Description	Milestone
M1	Jan 2016	Conduct intake interviews with hackAIR partners and selected stakeholders	
M2	Feb 2016	Set up a stakeholder database	
M4	Apr 2016	Map and prioritise network of interest, first selection	
M11	Nov 2016	Network of interest: First stakeholder meeting	
M12	Dec 2016	Network of interest established (first meeting report)	D8.4
M24	Dec 2017	Network of interest workshop report	D8.7
M36	Dec 2018	Network of interest closing meeting report	D8.9

6.1.6.4 Expected result

NGOs and other civil society organisations are engaged in and participate through hackAIR's network of interest communication and meetings.

Indicator	Means of verification	Target
Number of meetings network of interest	List of events	Total: 4
Total number of participants	List of participants	Total: 100

We will also report on participant feedback regarding their thoughts of the event and how it changed their perception on air quality issues.

6.2 Pilot phase

Activities in the pilot phase aim to create awareness and citizen engagement on air quality through the hackAIR open platform (Objective 2). These include:

2.1 Creating buzz and engagement around the platform, through:

2.1.1 Social media outreach

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1.2 Direct communication support of the pilot

2.2 Create hands-on opportunities to experience the platform, through

2.2.1 Workshops

During this phase, the hackAIR platform will be tested in a real-life environment in two pilot locations: Germany and Norway. Towards the end of the start-up phase a plan will be provided for the dissemination activities of the pilot phase with the purpose to support the pilot plan for hackAIR. As part of this plan, we will determine the brand identity of the hackAIR platform (including, for example, a new name and logo).

The pilot will be implemented with the direct participation of communities of citizens: BUND (Friends of the Earth Germany), a grassroots NGO with more than 400,000 members, which participates in the project as a partner, health interest groups (e.g. Norwegian Asthma and Allergy Associations – NAAF), an association with 19,000 users, and the user community developed in the CITI-SENSE project (Citizen Observatory on air quality – led by partner NILU).

In general, dissemination activities will support the pilot in Germany and Norway and include a hackAIR workshop tour, project rebranding, an additional website for the hackAIR platform, and online tutorials.

6.2.1 Output 2.1: Buzz and engagement

Building awareness and citizen engagement on air quality through the hackAIR open platform is another objective of hackAIR's communication strategy. To this end, two primary strategies will be implemented with the aim of creating buzz and engagement around the platform:

2.1.1 Social media outreach

2.1.2 Direct communication support to the pilot

6.2.2 Activity 2.1.1: Social media

hackAIR's social media presence will be managed, delivered and coordinated through different online social networks (OSN) and tools. At a minimum, all news and updates published on www.hackair.eu will be forwarded to these platforms while relevant social media content is connected to hackAIR's website for traffic and lead generation.

In order to ensure a return on social media efforts along the course of the project, an experimental approach will be used across hackAIR's social media channels with particular attention to what generates response, modifying, adapting, determining what shall continue or otherwise and finding new ways to engage.

6.2.2.1 Goals and audience

- 📍 Reach out and inform organisations and interested parties working on air quality;
- 📍 Develop links with the network of interest and a community of end users; and
- 📍 Engage audiences with relevant information on air quality, citizen science and behavioural change.

Initially hackAIR's social media presence will focus on the co-creation and creating awareness among organisations working on air quality (Startup phase), through Twitter. To further expand hackAIR's presence, branded presentations and documents will be spread through Slideshare, a directory of categorized presentations and documents that allows content to be distributed and shared online.

During the Pilot phase, once hackAIR's platform development is ready to actively engage end users, social media presence will focus in community building, expanding to reach users of the hackAIR platform through Facebook, Instagram and Youtube.

6.2.2.2 Activities

hackAIR's social media content and engagement strategy includes:

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

- 📍 Information, updates and presentations about hackAIR
- 📍 Updates and news on air quality and monitoring (links and alerts on articles)
- 📍 Citizen-oriented information on the environment
- 📍 Interesting data points
- 📍 Open conversations (Twitter chats or webinars), on air quality and participatory sensing
- 📍 Stories on citizen science and citizen observatories

The above-mentioned content will be sourced through information shared by hackAIR's partners and complemented with tools such as Google Alerts, ensuring ongoing access to relevant and up to date information, news and articles.

The main proposed social media channels are:

Platform	Core audience	Advantage	Profile
Twitter account	Organisations working on air quality	Ease of use and widespread around communities of interest	@hack AIR
Slideshare	Organisations and individuals interested in air quality, users of the hackAIR platform	Ease to upload presentations, wide reach and engagement of interested individuals	TBC
Facebook page	Organisations working on air quality and users of the hackAIR platform	Widespread reach and diversity of groups of interest	TBC
Instagram		Ease of use for image sharing (hackAIR's data source)	TBC
Youtube	Interested individuals and users of the hackAIR platform	Widespread among interested individuals through engaging visuals	TBC

hackAIR's partner CERTH has developed a social media monitoring tool that will be set up in the start-up phase to facilitate the assessment of engagement campaigns and audience management in social media. It will help discover online communities and measure audience and impact. Following a scan of air quality conversations on social media, the following set of keywords are suggested:

hackAIR OR citizens observatory OR citizens observatories or participatory sensing

Particulates OR Airpollution OR Airquality

Cleanair OR Knowyourair

Luftverschmutzung OR Feinstaub

Luftforurensning OR luftkvalitet

Partners of hackAIR are invited to actively engage and circulate hackAIR social media activity through their social media profiles and organisation's channels, thus leveraging on the current reach of partners networks across Europe.

A particular effort will be put in identifying and targeting digital opinion leaders and influencers (journalists, bloggers, activists, twitter, facebook users, etc.) who tend to have large audiences following them, with the aim contacted to establish contact and invite them to an online information session (engagement session) and invited to write about their experiences, spread hackAIR's message through mentions or retweets, increasing the project's reach.

To both, generate further engagement and ensure an ongoing stream of activity across hackAIR's social media networks, the Hootsuite platform will be used allowing to manage different social networks, schedule messages for future publishing, respond to mentions, questions and messages relevant to hackAIR, encouraging a bidirectional

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

communication and conversations with hackAIR's audiences, as well as collaboration among the hackAIR communication's team.

At a later stage, hackAIR's social media presence will be aligned with the engagement strategy for hackAIR community involvement (WP6 by VUB - M20). During this stage, social media activities will be evaluated. This will include determining the feasibility of a discussion group on Facebook to create an active community for stakeholders, members of the network of interest and digital opinion leaders, to exchange viewpoints, best practice and personal experience with hackAIR, allowing further to do preparations and follow ups around the events.

6.2.2.3 Indicative timeline

Month	Date	Description
M3	Mar 2016	Implement consistent social media content strategy for Twitter
M3	Mar 2016	Activate social media monitoring tool with keywords
M4	Apr 2016	Slideshare: account set up and hackAIR's presentation upload
M4	Apr 2016	Identify digital opinion leaders and influencers; initial webinar
M20	Aug 2017	Social media extension, set up Facebook page, Instagram and Youtube

6.2.2.4 Expected result

A growing awareness and engagement around the platform from organisations working on air quality and interested parties through hackAIR's social media impressions.

Indicator	Means of verification	Target
Social media impressions	Total reach of posts	Total: 200,000

We will also report on likes, followers, shares and comments in the biannual reports.

6.2.3 Activity 2.1.2: Direct communication support for the pilot

To create buzz and engagement around the pilot, hackAIR's communications team will align closely with activities in WP7 (pilot operation and evaluation). With a mix of direct outreach and media engagement, the pilot will invite citizens and interested users to participate in pilot activities, access air quality information through the hackAIR platform and submit information through their own sensors.

6.2.3.1 Goals and audience

The purpose is to a) reach a large number of potential users, b) inform them about air quality and the potential of participatory sensing and c) provide offers for them to participate in the hackAIR project.

In Germany, the core target audience will be existing environmental activists and groups interested in air quality (e.g. schools, universities and civil society organisations working on transport).

In Norway, we will focus on environmental health interest groups and the scientific community.

6.2.3.2 Activities

In collaboration with NILU and BUND's communications teams, we will identify a targeted communication plan for each pilot. In addition to the material already available for users on the hackAIR website, we will compile contents for a simple press pack to be translated into German and Norwegian.

In alignment with the pilot event schedule and news cycle, local communications teams will then identify newspapers, magazines, and online publications to be targeted and approach these to collaborate on articles.

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

ePress releases with dissemination to online media and bloggers, and dissemination of press information to digital opinion leaders publishing in unofficial media channels will also be explored to create additional outreach.

6.2.3.3 Indicative timeline

Month	Date	Description
M20	Aug 2017	Communication activities included in D7.1 pilot plan
M21	Sep 2017	Support pilot in Germany and Norway with a press pack

6.2.3.4 Expected result

Growing awareness and engagement around the platform among organisations working on air quality and community of end users through direct communications generating media and online impressions, during the pilot phase.

Indicator	Means of verification	Target
Media and online impressions	List of articles by outlet and estimated number of readers	Total: 1,000,000

6.2.4 Output 2.2: Hands-on opportunities to experience the platform

Providing hands-on opportunities to experience the platform will help fulfil the general objective to build awareness and citizen engagement on air quality through the hackAIR open platform. The following activities engage interested parties and users of hackAIR's platform through the hackAIR workshop tour while supporting the pilot implementation.

6.2.5 Activity 2.2.1: hackAIR workshop tour

At least seven to ten workshops will be held during the pilot phase, organised as part of hackAIR's workshop tour across Europe, with the overall purpose to test the hackAIR platform. We will develop a detailed plan for this tour in line with the pilot plan by August 2017.

6.2.5.1 Goals and audience

- Reach a large community of interested citizens to build awareness about the project, its benefits and results;
- Engage citizens, local air quality advocates, end users and members of organisations working on air quality;
- Allow them to explore the hackAIR tools with a hands-on approach (e.g. building their own air quality monitoring station or participating in an air-quality photography excursion);
- Provide opportunities for media coverage.
- Activities

Workshops are envisaged to take place in Germany (multiple times), Oslo, Brussels, and other selected European locations such as Thessaloniki or Amsterdam. Local host organisations will invite the involvement, both of local air quality advocates and of the maker community.

In order to reach a wider range of participants and depending on the capacity of the local hosts, we will explore streaming these workshops online as well as recording parts of the workshops in video to upload in the Youtube channel to create additional outreach.

Additional cities will be identified through the hackAIR network of interest to run workshops and test the platform. hackAIR will invite targeted organisations to host a workshop. hackAIR will provide the content and access to air quality sensors, local hosts will be asked to organise the logistics around the place and to invite participants.

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Based on the lessons learned from organising workshops, an online toolkit for workshops will be developed with the purpose of empowering organisations to host workshops and use the project to raise awareness.

6.2.5.2 Indicative timeline

Month	Date	Description	Deliverable
M20	Aug 2017	Plan for hackAIR workshop tour	D8.5
M23	Nov 2017	hackAIR workshop toolkit	D8.6
M30	Jun 2018	Present workshop results	

6.2.5.3 Expected result

Hands-on opportunities through which interested parties and users of the hackAIR platform can participate and experience the platform during the hackAIR workshop tour.

Indicator	Means of verification	Target
Number of workshops organised	List of events	Total: 7-10
Number of workshop participants	List of participants	Total: 500

6.3 Sustainability phase

Throughout the project, but especially towards the end of the project, we will focus on disseminating and exploiting the results of the project and building interest in the use of the open hackAIR platform and in monitoring data beyond the lifetime of the hackAIR project (Objective 3). Activities include:

3.1 Expanding the network through:

3.1.1 External meetings

3.1.2 Sustainability and exploitation strategy

6.3.1 Output 3.1: Expand the network

To expand the hackAIR network beyond the existing network of interest hackAIR partners will present the project, outcomes, and technologies at external events and develop a strategic approach to sustainability and exploitation.

6.3.2 Activity 3.1.1: External meetings

6.3.2.1 Goals and audience

Throughout the project, hackAIR will build connections to related communities of practice, present the project there and build connections in order to build a better product based on the feedback, expand the community of users and prepare for the future exploitation of the platform.

6.3.2.2 Activities

In addition to the activities mentioned above (especially the Network of Interest and the workshop tour), all hackAIR partners intend to present the project, its technology and background and their involvement in it. As no full event schedule is available for the entirety of the project, the list below only contains a limited set of events in 2016.

ONSUB will maintain the list of upcoming events on the hackAIR website, and update it based on partners' input after each consortium meeting.

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

6.3.2.3 Initial list of events

Month	Date	Description
M4	Apr 2016	Making Sense. Advances and explorations in participatory sensing during the Design and the City conference (Amsterdam, Netherlands)
M5	May 2016	1st International Workshop on the Social Web for Environmental and Ecological Monitoring (SWEEM) (Cologne, Germany)
M9	Sep 2016	1st International Workshop on Internet and Social media for Environmental Monitoring (ISEM 2016), Florence, 12-14/9/2016, during the 3rd International Conference on Internet Science INSCI16 http://internetscienceconference.eu .

6.3.2.4 Expected result

Indicator	Means of verification	Target
Number of external meetings with hackAIR representation	List of events	Total: 10

A ANNEXES

A.1 Log Frame

	Project summary	Indicators	Means of verification	Target
Goal of the Project	To enable communities of citizens to easily set up air quality monitoring networks and engage their members in measuring and publishing outdoor air pollution levels.	Number of users participating in hackAIR	Registered users on hackAIR platform	Total: 8.290 (8.000 basic + 290 advanced users)
Communication Objectives	1. Encourage stakeholder coordination around air quality monitoring and citizen participation and invite participation in the hackAIR open platform;	Number of hackAIR stakeholders reached in project events and through the platform	Contact list	Total: 150
	2. Build awareness and citizen's engagement on air quality through the hackAIR open platform; and	User downloads of hackAIR application	Downloads through app store	Total: 30,000
	3. Build interest in the use of the hackAIR open platform and monitoring data beyond the lifetime of the hackAIR project.	NGOs and other civil society organisations adopting hackAIR platform	Declarations of interest	Total: 5
Activities and Outputs	1.1 Provide information about the project			
	1.1.1 Project website	Total visits (including returning visitors) to the project website	Piwik Analytics	Total: 36,000
	1.1.2 Communication materials	Quality and comprehensiveness	Biannual survey of project partners	Average ratings of 4 or above on Likert scale
	1.2 Regularly engage target audiences			
	1.2.1 Newsletter	Newsletter impressions	Number of subscribers by issue	Total: 3,000
	1.2.2 Network of Interest	Number of meetings network of interest Total number of participants	List of events List of participants	Total: 4 Total: 100
	2.1 Create buzz and engagement around the platform			
	2.1.1 Social media outreach	Social media impressions	Total reach of posts	Total: 200,000
	2.1.2 Direct communication support to the pilot	Media- and online impressions	List of articles by outlet and estimated number of readers	Total: 1,000,000
	2.2 Organise hands-on opportunities to experience the platform			
	2.2.1 Workshops	Number of organised workshops Number of workshop participants	List of events List of participants	Total: 7-10 Total: 500
	3.1 Expand the network			
	3.1.1 External meetings	Number of external meetings with hackAIR representation	List of events	Total: 10
3.1.2 Sustainability and exploitation strategy	Number of companies interested in using hackAIR	Declarations of interest	Total: 14	

A.2 Timeline

Activity	Month	Date	Description	Deliverable
1.1.1 Project website	M1	Jan 16	Placeholder website online	
1.2.2 Network of Interest	M1	Jan 16	Conduct intake interviews with hackAIR partners and selected stakeholders	
1.2.2 Network of Interest	M2	Feb 16	Set up a stakeholder database	
0. Project Management	M3	Mar 16	Communication and dissemination strategy	D8.1
1.1.1 Project website	M3	Mar 16	Launch of project website	
1.1.2 Communication material	M3	Mar 16	Visual identity and branding	
2.1.1 Social media outreach	M3	Mar 16	Implement a consistent social media content strategy for Twitter	
2.1.1 Social media outreach	M3	Mar 16	Activate social media monitoring tool with keywords	
1.1.2 Communication material	M4	Apr 16	hackAIR presentation	
1.2.1 Newsletter	M4	Apr 16	Newsletter issue #1	
1.2.2 Network of interest	M4	Apr 16	Mapping and priority selection network of interest, first selection	
2.1.1 Social media outreach	M4	Apr 16	Identify digital opinion leaders and influencers; initial webinar	
2.1.1 Social media outreach	M4	Apr 16	Slideshare: account set up and hackAIR's presentation upload	
3.1.1 External meetings	M4	Apr 16	Making Sense. Advances and explorations in participatory sensing during the Design and the City conference (Amsterdam, Netherlands)	
3.1.1 External meetings	M5	May 16	1st International Workshop on the Social Web for Environmental and Ecological Monitoring (SWEEM) (Cologne, Germany)	
3.1.2 Sustainability and exploitation strategy	M5	May 16	Initial business modelling workshop at project meeting	
0. Project Management	M6	Jun 16	1 st internal progress report	
1.1.2 Communication material	M6	Jun 16	Brochure + postcards; Information package	
0. Project Management	M21	Sep 16	Update to communication strategy	
1.2.1 Newsletter	M9	Sep 16	Newsletter issue #2	
3.1.1 External meetings	M9	Sep 16	1st International Workshop on Internet and Social media for Environmental Monitoring (ISEM 2016), Florence, 12-14/9/2016, during the 3rd International Conference on Internet Science INSCI16 http://internetscienceconference.eu .	
3.1.2 Sustainability and exploitation strategy	M9	Sep 16	Sustainability & Exploitation Strategy (1st version)	D8.2
1.1.2 Communication material	M10	Oct 16	Dissemination pack	D8.3
1.2.2 Network of interest	M11	Nov 16	Network of interest: First stakeholder meeting	
0. Project Management	M12	Dec 16	2 nd internal progress report	
1.2.2 Network of interest	M12	Dec 16	Network of interest established (first meeting report)	D8.4

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

1.2.1 Newsletter	M15	Mar 17	Newsletter issue #3	
0. Project Management	M18	Jun 17	3 rd internal progress report	
0. Project Management	M18	Jun 17	Periodic technical and financial report for M1-18	
1.1.2 Communication material	M18	Jun 17	Provide “summary for publication”	
1.1.1 Project website	M20	Aug 17	Additional website for the hackAIR platform	
1.1.2 Communication material	M20	Aug 17	Project rebranding; Posters	
2.1.1 Social media outreach	M20	Aug 17	Social media extension, setup Facebook page, Instagram and Youtube	
2.1.2 Direct communication support to the pilot	M20	Aug 17	Communication activities included in D7.1 pilot plan	
2.2.1 Workshops	M20	Aug 17	Plan for hackAIR workshop tour	D8.5
1.1.2 Communication material	M21	Sep 17	Online tutorial	
1.2.1 Newsletter	M21	Sep 17	Newsletter issue #4	
2.1.2 Direct communication support to the pilot	M21	Sep 17	Support pilot in Germany and Norway (report, material, promotion, press pack)	
2.2.1 Workshops	M23	Nov 17	hackAIR workshop toolkit	D8.6
0. Project Management	M24	Dec 17	4 th internal progress report	
1.2.2 Network of interest	M24	Dec 17	Network of interest workshop report	D8.7
1.1.2 Communication material	M27	Mar 18	Video showing initial project results	
1.2.1 Newsletter	M27	Mar 18	Newsletter issue #5	
3.1.2 Sustainability and exploitation strategy	M28	Apr 18	Second business modelling workshop + stakeholder interviews	
0. Project Management	M30	Jun 18	5 th internal progress report	
2.2.1 Workshops	M30	Jun 18	Present workshop results	
1.2.1 Newsletter	M33	Sep 18	Newsletter issue #6	
3.1.2 Sustainability and exploitation strategy	M35	Nov 18	Sustainability & exploitation strategy (final version)	D8.8
0. Project Management	M36	Dec 18	6 th internal progress report	
0. Project Management	M36	Dec 18	Periodic technical and financial report for M19-36	
1.1.2 Communication material	M36	Dec 18	Provide “summary for publication” including final results	
1.2.2 Network of interest	M36	Dec 18	Network of interest closing meeting report	D8.9

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

A.3 Gantt chart

	Q1 2016	Q2 2016	Q3 2016	Q4 2016	Q1 2017	Q2 2017	Q3 2017	Q4 2017	Q1 2018	Q2 2018	Q3 2018	Q4 2018
1.1.1 Project website	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
1.1.2 Communication material		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
1.2.1 Newsletter					█						█	
1.2.2 Network of Interest	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
2.1.1 Social media outreach		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
2.1.2 Direct communication support to the pilot							█	█	█	█	█	
2.2.1 Workshops							█	█		█		
3.1.1 External meetings		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
3.1.2 Sustainability and exploitation strategy		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█

A.4 Budget and partner contributions

Six partner organisations contribute to the implementation of work package 8 (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation). We expect the relative effort to be distributed as follows:

	ONSUB	DRAXIS	NILU	CERTH	BUND	VUB
Dissemination strategy + monitoring	1.25	0.10	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
1.1.1 Project website	1.25	1.25	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.10
1.1.2 Communication material	2.00	0.10	0.25	0.10	0.00	0.25
1.2.1 Newsletter	2.25	0.25	0.25	0.10	0.10	0.10
1.2.2 Network of interest	1.50	0.70	1.25	1.00	1.30	0.15
2.1.1 Social media outreach	1.25	0.10	0.25	0.10	0.00	0.10
2.1.2 Direct communications support to pilot	1.00	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.05	0.50
2.2.1 Workshops	2.50	0.50	0.25	0.00	0.10	0.25
3.1.1 External meetings	0.50	0.50	1.00	0.50	0.15	0.25
3.1.2 Sustainability and exploitation strategy	3.50	3.50	1.25	0.15	0.25	0.25
Total	17.00	7.00	5.00	2.00	2.00	2.00

A.5 Visual identity guidelines

The visual identity aims to provide guidelines that will help all hackAIR project partners build a strong and consistent branding, messages and visuals for hackAIR. They replace the initial guidance included in deliverable D1.2 Project management handbook.

A.5.1 Logo

hackAIR's logo plays a central role in the project's visual identity. It aids recollection and recall. The logo should be included in all external communications from the project. It can be included in external communications by partners about the project.

A.5.2 Logo versions

Files for the hackAIR logo can be found in the project's shared Dropbox account under hackAIR > Communications.

Figure 6.1 Full colour version

Figure 6.2 Grey scale version

Figure 6.3 Full colour version with coloured background

The small logo version has white balloon lines and thicker letters to increase legibility.

Figure 6.4 Small logo version

A.5.3 Logo rules

Use your judgement to determine when to use which logo: If you can't read it, you can't use it.

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Figure 6.5 Do not alter or rotate the logo

General rules

The logo should never be altered in any way.

Please don't rotate the logo.

Use the balloon as you wish, but don't rotate it.

Figure 6.6 Logo size for printed matter

Printed matter

Start using the logo without the tagline when the total width is less than 20mm.

Start using the small logo when the total width is less than 11mm.

The minimum size use of the small logo is 6mm width.

Online

Start using the logo without the tagline when the total width is less than 120px.

Start using the small logo when the hackAIR word's width is less than 60px.

The minimum size use of the small logo is 40px width.

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Figure 5. Recommended safe space around the logo

Please allow "d1" empty space around the logo.

A.5.4 Colour palette

Please use the following colour palette for any graphics or colour designs or backgrounds that you use to communication about hackAIR.

Light backgrounds	Bright orange #FF6666 R: 255 G: 102 B:102 C: 0 M: 75 Y: 50 K: 0	Dark green #00A3AC R: 0 G: 163 B: 172 C: 80 M: 10 Y: 35 K: 0	Grey #4D4D4D R: 77 G: 77 B:77 C: 0 M: 0 Y: 0 K: 85
	Dark backgrounds	Yellow #FFFFC3 R: 255 G: 255 B: 195 C: 0 M: 0 Y: 24 K: 0	White #FFFFFF R: 255 G: 255 B: 255 C: 0 M: 0 Y: 0 K: 0

A.5.5 Typography

hackAIR's primary typefaces are **Calibri** and **Century**.

Typeface	Alternative	Recommended usage
Century	Times	Use it for headings only, in Bright Orange (#FF6666)
Calibri	Trebuchet MS	Use it for body text, in web and print communication, in Grey (#4D4D4D)
BookendsWithAccents	N/A	The logo is based on this font. Never use it, except in call-to-action tags, as a direct connection to our logo. You might need to add an outline to make it thicker. It can be found at Fontspace . Please support the font designer.
GEOMETR451BLACK	N/A	It is used for the tagline only.

A.5.6 Photography guidelines

When using photos together with your hackAIR communication, choose good quality, symbolic and positive pictures.

Use pictures that	Avoid pictures that
Depict clear skies (possibly in combination with hot air balloons);	Depict pristine, rural environments;
Relate to the urban environment (possibly in combination with kids or amateur athletes enjoying it);	Show smog, car exhausts and industrial pollution;
Show people engaged in measurements or air quality improvements (e.g. project activities).	Show people in meeting rooms or static group pictures.

A.5.7 Style guide

In written communication, hackAIR uses British English, following the Oxford Style Guide in cases of doubt. The most important rules:

- ♥ **Capital letters.** Do not use a capital letter unless absolutely required. Capitalise the first word of a headline.
- ♥ **Numbers.**
 - ♥ Spell out whole-number words for one to ten; use figures for numbers above ten.
 - ♥ Use figures and symbols for percentages, measurements and currency: €5 million.
 - ♥ Use a point to separate whole numbers from decimals, and a comma to indicate thousands: 152,231.32
- ♥ **Dates and time.**
 - ♥ Use the 24-hour clock for times (13:00).
 - ♥ Always put the date before the month: 13 April 2007.

A.6 Boilerplate text

hackAIR in one sentence (140 characters)

hackAIR is an open technology platform that you can use to access, collect and improve information on air quality in Europe.

Short description (150 words)

Air pollution is an environmental issue with serious health and lifespan implications. It remains difficult for citizens to assess their exposure to air pollution and air quality issues in their country.

The hackAIR open platform will enable communities of citizens to easily engage their members in generating and publishing information relevant to outdoor air pollution, leveraging the power of citizen science, online social networks, mobile and open hardware technologies, and engagement strategies.

hackAIR aims to complement official data with community-driven data sources, for collecting, analysing and sharing air quality measurements to community members through low cost open hardware sensors easily assembled by citizens, web and/or mobile phones.

By October 2017, hackAIR will be tested in two European countries (Germany and Norway) in order to validate the service platform and how this can contribute towards individual and collective awareness about air quality in Europe, encouraging changes in behaviour towards air quality improvements.

Long description (525 words)

Over the next three years, the European Union will invest in an open technology platform for citizen observatories on air quality through the €2 million project hackAIR.

Air pollution is an environmental issue with serious health and lifespan implications. However, it remains difficult for citizens to access improved information on air quality and assess their exposure to air pollution where they live.

hackAIR will enable communities of citizens to easily engage their members in generating and publishing information relevant to outdoor air pollution, leveraging the power of citizen science, online social networks, mobile and open hardware technologies, and engagement strategies.

The hackAIR platform will be co-created by users and made available through: a web application that communities of citizens will be able to install and customise and a mobile app that citizens can use to get convenient access to easy-to-understand air quality information. Users will also be able to contribute to measurements with an open sensor, or by taking and uploading sky-depicting photos. Ultimately, hackAIR will help encourage changes in behaviour towards air quality improvements.

Benefits

The hackAIR platform aims to complement official data with community-driven data sources, for collecting, analysing, and sharing air quality measurements to community members. Citizens benefit from the platform through easy engagement and participation in monitoring atmospheric particulate matter, receiving real-time information on the current status of air quality, participating in a community of like-minded users who are concerned about the effects of air pollution, receiving personalised recommendations on actions that they can perform as individual members.

Official air quality sensors are often few and distantly scattered, coverage is poor outside cities, and the data is not always easily accessible. hackAIR takes advantage of existing open and complementary community-driven data that is then processed via sensing models and tools, a data fusion model and reasoning, to extract and normalise information for collective awareness for air quality in Europe.

Users

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

hackAIR will enable communities of citizens to easily engage their members in generating and publishing information relevant to outdoor air pollution including:

- 📍 Citizens (e.g. elderly, parents of small children, outdoor sport enthusiasts, conservationists) and app/service developers, can submit data through the hackAIR platform
- 📍 Open source community and operators of personal weather stations, can build an air quality monitoring station.
- 📍 Environmental organisations, health associations, maker spaces, educational organisations, can organise local hackAIR workshops to build awareness.
- 📍 The scientific community (universities, research institutes, NGOs, independent researchers) can use data to gain insights on air quality patterns; use the hackAIR platform and use communication channels to create a dialogue.
- 📍 Enterprises interested in hackAIR products and services for other health related apps, etc., can use products and services created by hackAIR.
- 📍 Local government and transport-related agencies can use data to inform public policy.

In the first phase of the project, hackAIR will demonstrate this approach in two pilot locations in Europe. The hackAIR platform will be developed as open source software, anyone will be able to study, download, change and distribute the source code, or to use it to create and maintain air quality monitoring networks.

The project will be implemented over three years, with the final results expected in December 2018.

Project information

Full title: Collective awareness platform for outdoor air pollution (No 688363)

Funded under: ICT-10-2015 Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation, sub objective a: Collective awareness pilots for bottom-up participatory innovation paradigms.

Total cost: 2,000,406.25 €

Execution: From 1 January 2016 to 31 December 2018

Consortium

Consortium Coordinator

DRAXIS Environmental S.A., Greece

Participating Partners

Norsk Institutt For Luftforskning, Norway

Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis, Greece

BUND für Umwelt und Naturschutz Deutschland e.V., Germany

SMIT Center for Studies on Media, Information and Telecommunication at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Belgium

ON:SUBJECT, The Netherlands

Contact details

Website: <http://www.hackair.eu>

Twitter: [@hack air](https://twitter.com/hack_air)

Project Coordinator: Dr Machi Simeonidou

DRAXIS Environmental S.A.

Email: msimeonidou@draxis.gr

Press and public relations: Wiebke Herding

ON: SUBJECT

Email: wiebke@onsubject.eu

A.7 Structure for hackAIR stakeholder database

Name
Category: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. org health/environment 2. research/monitoring 3. data providers
Short description
Location
Link
Core group? (yes, possibly, no)
Similar project? (yes, no)
Contact person (only visible for team)
E-Mail (only visible for team)
hackAIR partner
Comments

A.8 Reporting templates

Reporting form: Event

Title of the event	
Event	DD/MM/YY
Event location	City, country
Description	Include information on type of event, objectives, scope, structure and organisers, as applicable
Speakers	Name, organisation, position
Participants	Number of participants, target audience
Results / outcomes	What is the impact of the event on the project? e.g. does it create awareness about the project's outcomes, encourage involvement, create synergies with organisation or projects, collaboration agreements with third existing parties, strengthen links with public bodies, or consolidate exploitation position, etc.?
Documents or links for further information	Agenda, web link for more info, presentations, evaluation overview/participant comments

Reporting form: Article or publication

Date	DD/MM/YY
Description	Type of publication / published where / title of article
Estimated reach	Number of people the activity has reached (e.g. newspaper circulation)
Target audience	Describe the type of audience this activity has reached (e.g. citizens of Oslo)
Results	Did you receive any responses? Was the story picked up somewhere else?
Link	If the publication/article is online, please provide a link. Otherwise, please send a scan of the publication/article to your report.

A.9 hackAIR communication policy

The beneficiaries must promote hackAIR and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner. All partners are allowed and encouraged to communicate with interested third parties and to address to stakeholders and potential end users within the context of the project and in service of the project objectives.

Any communication activity led by partners must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that neither the Research Executive Agency nor the European Commission is responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. In addition, all communication activities led by partners must be included in the biannual dissemination reports.

In all external communications, a reference to the project and the European funding should be made, quoting the project acronym and the grant agreement number (688363), using the project visual identity and the European flag. Example:

The project hackAIR has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 688363.

Before major communication activities (such as events, press releases, scientific articles or the production of printed materials), partners must coordinate with the Dissemination Manager and the Project Coordinator. If a communication activity is expected to have a major media impact, the Project Coordinator will inform the European Commission.

For scientific publications related to hackAIR, beneficiaries must ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user). The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- ♥ the terms 'European Union (EU)' and 'Horizon 2020';
- ♥ the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- ♥ the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- ♥ a persistent identifier.

A.9.1 Sign-off process

When deciding on dissemination, the beneficiaries must also consider the other beneficiaries' legitimate interests. The partners agree to the following sign-off process for communication in the name of hackAIR:

D8.1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Static website text, brochure and other static publications	Draft shared with all partners 7 days before publication; final sign-off through project coordinator
Press releases and news stories	Draft shared with all partners 3 days before publication; final sign-off through project coordinator
Project newsletter	Invitation to contribute to all partners sent 3 weeks before publication; final sign-off through project coordinator
Social media updates	Published directly through dissemination manager in line with the communication strategy

A.9.2 Contact database

To keep track of external contacts, partners are requested to add details of external contacts to the shared contact database, stored on Dropbox.